

FISP-ProCOP - User Guide

This is a user guide for the framework for information security and privacy management called **FISP-ProCOP**¹. The files referred to in this document can be found in [this Google Drive folder](#).

The framework is a tool for depicting aspects and measures of information security and privacy management in organisations contributing to a smart system. Except for **depicting measures used for information security and privacy assurance**, FISP-ProCOP **helps to identify inconsistencies between the measures**.

The framework consists of the FISP-ProCOP matrix and the instructions on its usage for the inconsistencies identification. The matrix is shown in Figure 1.

Dimension	Category	#	Attribute
P. People	PA. Actors	1	Actors, stakeholders, entities
		2	Goals, tasks, motives
	PR. Relationships	3	Relationships and dependencies between actors
O. Organisation	OS. Strategy	4	Purpose for the system usage, org. design & strategy
		5	Challenges to address
	OC. Formal Constraints	6	Legislation, regulation, standard
	OI. Information Involved	7	Type of information used
		8	How the information is manipulated
		9	Security criteria
		10	Privacy objectives
C. Sec. & Privacy Countermeasures	CP. Policies & Practices	11	Policies & practices
	CE. Training & Education	12	Training & education
	CT. Technology	13	Architectural measures
		14	Use case-oriented technological measures
		15	Cryptographic building blocks
		16	Others technological measures
Pr. Processes	PrL. System Lifecycle	17	Security as a part of the system lifecycle
	PrU. Usage of the System	18	Use cases of the system as a part of the business processes

Figure 1. FISP-ProCOP matrix

The targeted users of **FISP-ProCOP** are called hereinafter “expert group” and include:

- (i) business analyst (BA);
- (ii) chief information security officer (CISO);
- (iii) data protection officer (DPO);
- (iv) security architect.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.7250/csimq.2024-38.04>

The representatives of these (or similar) roles in the organisation should use the framework following the process depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Process of using FISP-ProCOP

Alternatively, the one of the mentioned role representatives can execute the whole process on its own which, however, may lead to the worsen quality of the results.

FISP-ProCOP matrix can be created in two ways:

- I. manually;
- II. questionnaire-based.

I. Manual FISP-ProCOP usage

1. Open the Excel file “*FISP-ProCOP matrix - manual template.xlsx*”.

2. Make a copy of this template.
3. Open the create copy of this file.
4. For the manual matrix creation, the users should use the file “*FISP-ProCOP matrix - manual template.xlsx*”, sheet “*Answers in matrix*”. Following the process in Figure 1, the expert group creates the FISP-ProCOP matrix by filling-in the attributes. If needed, the new columns for attributes can be added.

Dimension	Category	#	Attribute	Attribute instances			
P. People	PA. Actors	1	Actors, stakeholders, entities				
		2	Goals, tasks, motives				
	PR. Relationships	3	Relationships and dependencies between actors				
O. Organisation	OS. Strategy	4	Purpose for the system usage, org. design & strategy				
		5	Challenges to address				
	OC. Formal Constraints	6	Legislation, regulation, standard				
		7	Type of information used				
	OI. Information Involved	8	How the information is manipulated				
		9	Security criteria				
		10	Privacy objectives				
C. Sec. & Privacy Counter-measures	CP. Policies & Practices	11	Policies & practices				
		12	Training & education				
	CT. Technology	13	Architectural measures				
		14	Use case-oriented technological measures				
		15	Cryptographic building blocks				
Pr. Processes	PrL. System Lifecycle	16	Others technological measures				
		17	Security as a part of the system lifecycle				
	PrU. Usage of the System	18	Use cases of the system as a part of the business processes				

5. All the attributes defined by the expert group members are put in one final matrix (Step “*Merge matrices*” in Fig. 2).
6. Based on the created matrix, the expert group answers questions (select Yes/No) in the sheet “*Validation*”, providing the explanations for the validation result.

FISP-ProCOP matrix - manual template .xlsx

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#	Cross-validation questions between attributes	Validation result	Your explanation for validation failure
1	I. Are the mentioned actors (1) include the providers of the security measures (13, 14, 15, 16)?	▼	
2	II. Are the mentioned actors (1) include all the parties involved in business processes (18) for the end-users within the smart system?	▼	
3	III. Are all the actors (1) trusted to share the information (7) with for their purposes (2)?	▼	
4	IV. Did you depict the relationships (3) between all the actors (users, stakeholders, service providers) (1) including the ones outside of smart system scope?	▼	
5	V. Does the mentioned system purpose consider the interests (2) of the actors (1)?	▼	
6	VI. If the number of active end-users poses a challenge to the smart system, is it mentioned in as a challenge (5)?	▼	
7	VII. Is the level of your organisation's involvement in the smart system lifecycle reflected in the policies & practices (11) used for the partners?	▼	
8	VIII. Do you mention owners of the systems your smart system has integrations with as actors (1)?	▼	
9	IX. Can the mentioned challenges be solved by using the respective standards (6)?	▼	
10	XI. Are the mentioned challenges addressed by any measures in (11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16)?	▼	

Answers in matrix Validation 1

7. The validation results with “No” are the identified inconsistencies among the measures for information security and privacy management. Such inconsistencies can be used as the baseline for the requirements.

II. Questionnaire-based FISP-ProCOP usage

Step I. Create and answer the survey.

1. Open the Google Forms “FISP-ProCOP - Questionnaire template”.

2. Make a copy of this template.
3. Open the create copy of this Google Forms and copy the responder link (following steps in the screenshot below).

4. Use the copied link to open the survey.
5. Answer the questions in the opened survey

Step II. Reviewing the analyzed results within the developed FISP-ProCOP matrix

1. After answering the survey questions, open the copy of the Google Form (from the step I.3) and create a spreadsheet with your answers as a new spreadsheet.

Select destination for responses X

Create a new spreadsheet Copy of FISP-ProCOP - Questi... Learn more

2. Open the created spreadsheet with answers

3. Open the "FISP-ProCOP Analyser - template.xlsx" spreadsheet from the shared Google Drive folder.

4. Make a copy of the spreadsheet and open it

5. Copy row 2 from created spreadsheet with answers (Step II.2)

6. Paste the copied row with answer into the cell B3 in the created copy of FISP-ProCOP Analyser.

7. Now you can see (1) the FISP-ProCOP matrix filled in based on the answers to the survey questions (columns H and I in the sheet "Answers in matrix") in the created copy of FISP-ProCOP Analyser.

Dimension	Category	#	Attribute	Corresponding question(s)	Attribute instances	Cross-validation questions between attributes
F. People	PA. Actors	1	Actors, stakeholders, entities	2-11, 2-21, 2-31	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AWS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms user, service provider, IAAS	I. Did you include all the actors (1) who provide the security measures (13, 14, 15, 16)? II. Did you include all the actors (1) involved in business processes (18) for the end-users within the smart system? III. Which of the actors (1) is fully trusted to share the information (7) with? IV. Did you depict the relationships (2) between all the actors (users, stakeholders, service providers) (4) including the ones outside of smart system scope? V. Does the mentioned system purpose consider the interests (2) of the actors (1)? VI. Does the number of active end-users pose a challenge (2) to the smart system? VII. Is the level of your organisation's involvement in the smart system lifecycle reflected in the policies & practices (11) used for the partners? VIII. Do you mention owners of the systems your organisation use as actors (1)? IX. Do you mention owners of the systems your smart system has integrations with as actors (1)? X. Can the mentioned challenges be solved by using the respective standards (6)? XI. Are the mentioned challenges addressed by any measures in (11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16)? XII. Do the legislations, regulations, and standards (6) include sector-specific (4) regulations and standards w.r.t. the system purposes? XIII. Who from (1) is the origin or provider of this information? How do you verify the origin? XIV. Does the information manipulation by actors in (1) directly correspond to their goals in (5)? XV. Do the manipulation operations (8) over the information (7) correspond to the system purpose (4)? XVI. Can the dependencies (3) between actors (1) violate security criteria (9)? XVII. Do the defined security criteria (9) consider all the requirements for the information types (7) w.r.t. legislations and standards (6)? XVIII. Did you define the rules of PII (8) visibility (10) for all the actors (1)? XIX. Can the dependencies (3) between actors (1) violate privacy criteria (10)? XX. Do the defined security criteria (9) consider all the requirements for the information types (7) w.r.t. legislations and standards (6)? XXI. Are the policies & practices (11) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXII. Do you have training & education (12) measures for all the actors in (1) (users, stakeholders, external entities)? XXIII. Do the training & education (12) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXIV. Do the architectural measures (13) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXV. Do the use case-oriented measures (14) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXVI. Do the used cryptographic measures (15) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXVII. Do the other technological measures (15) include all the mandatory ones from regulations and standards (6)? XXVIII. Does the system lifecycle (17) include all the mandatory activities, practices, etc. from the followed regulations and standards (6)?
		2	Goals, tasks, motives	3-4	TA is governed by a city government Objective: ride-hailing in the cities; Active end-user: 1,001 - 10,000; Involvement in the system lifecycle: We have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development; Number of integrations: +2	
	PR. Relationships	3	Relationships and dependencies between actors	2-5	interoperability, availability	
O. Organisation	OS. Strategy	4	Purpose for the system usage, org. design & strategy	1-1, 1-2, 1-3, 1-4	European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010) (a.k.a. ITS Directive), NIS2 directive, 7742/18/2014 Sb. (zákon o kybernetické bezpečnosti), ISO/IEC 27001, No, not certified	
		5	Challenges to address	1-5	interoperability, availability	
	OC. Formal Constraints	6	Legislation, regulation, standard	3-1, 3-2, 3-3	Driver ID we save DriverID for checking the eligibility of driving	
		7	Type of information used	2-6, 1-11, 2-6, 3-11	Confidentiality, Integrity Controller: We are; Processor: FLT; Can be shared with: FLT & City government	
		8	How the information is manipulated	2-6, 1-2, 2-6, 3-2	Not a PII Policies & Practices: NIST CSF, Security Development Lifecycle; Principles: Least privilege, Data minimisation; Knowledge management practices: System documentation, Unwritten rules followed by the teams	
	OI. Information Involved	9	Security criteria	2-6, 1-3, 2-6, 3-2	Coordination of policies with partners: auditing	
		10	Privacy objectives	2-6, 1-4, 2-6, 1-5, 2-6, 3-2, 7	Trainings for users: Introducing the privacy policy during the first-time onboarding to the system; Trainings for employees: we don't have Architecture: Public Key Infrastructure (PKI); Managing identities of partners: access control & logging Payment-related measures: Card-based payment Document creation-related measures: usual document	
C. Sec. & Privacy Counter-measures	CP. Policies & Practices	11	Policies & practices	4-1, 4-2, 4-3, 5-10	Confidentiality, Integrity Controller: We are; Processor: FLT; Can be shared with: FLT & City government	
		12	Training & education	4-3, 4-4	Coordination of policies with partners: auditing	
	CT. Technology	13	Architectural measures	5-1, 5-2, 5-3	Document creation-related measures: usual document	
14		Use case-oriented technological measures	2-6, 1-1, 2-6, 3-1, 4-7, 11, 4-7, 21	Document creation-related measures: usual document		
15		Cryptographic building blocks	2-6, 1-5, 2-6	Document creation-related measures: usual document		
PrL. System Lifecycle	CT. Technology	16	Others technological measures	3-2, 3-4, 5-8	Secure communication: Not applicable; Other: firewall Principles of system development and support: Security testing, Separation of development, test and production environments; Security monitoring: Vulnerability scanner	
		17	Security as a part of the system lifecycle	6-1, 6-2	Secure communication: Not applicable; Other: firewall Principles of system development and support: Security testing, Separation of development, test and production environments; Security monitoring: Vulnerability scanner	

The column J (2) contains the cross-validation questions, which should help you identify the inconsistencies between the goal, constraints and measures used for information security and privacy management in your organisation.

- Go to the “Validation” sheet, and answer Yes/No (1) in column D to the cross-validation questions in column B. Use the hints (2) pre-filled-in based on the FISP-ProCOP matrix.

D7		fx No													
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1															
2		Cross-validation questions between attributes	Your explanation for validation failure	Validation result	Cross-validation questions between attributes (filled in)										
3		I. Are the mentioned actors (c) include the providers of the security measures (4), 14, 15, 40?		Yes	Are the mentioned actors	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AVIS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms	includes the providers of the following security measures:	Architecture: Public Key Infrastructure (PKI); Managing identities of partners: access control & logging; Payment-related measures: Card-based payment, Document creation-related measures: usual document; Classical cryptography: RSA, digital signature; Post-quantum cryptography: No; FQDN: Role-based access control; Secure communication: Not applicable; Other: Firewall							
4		II. Are the mentioned actors (c) include all the parties involved in business processes (40) for the end-users within the smart system?	Our employees participate in car services, but are not included as actors	No	Are the mentioned actors	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AVIS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms	includes all the parties involved in business processes	Ride fulfilment, gas fill-in, car service							for the end-users within the smart system?
5		III. Are all the actors (c) treated to share the information (7) with for their purpose (4)?		No	Are the mentioned actors	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AVIS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms	fully treated to share the information	Car plates, Driver ID							with for their following purpose
6		IV. Did you depict the relationships (c) between all the actors (users, stakeholders, service providers) (a) including the ones outside of smart system scope?		Yes	Did you depict all the relationships	TA is governed by a city government	between all the actors (users, stakeholders, service providers)	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AVIS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms							including the ones outside of smart system scope?
7		V. Does the mentioned system purpose consider the interests (c) of the actors (4)?		No	Does the mentioned system purpose	Objective: ride-bailing in the cities; Involvement in the system lifecycle: We have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development	consider the interests	user, service provider, laaS							of the actors
8		VI. If the number of active end-users poses a challenge to the smart system, is it mentioned in as a challenge (3)?		Yes	VI. If the number of active end-users	Number of users: 1,000 – 10,000	poses a challenge to the smart system, is it mentioned in as a challenge	interoperability, availability							?
9		VII. Is the level of your organization's involvement in the smart system lifecycle reflected in the policies & practices (a) used for the partners?		Yes	VII. Is the level of your organization's involvement in the smart system lifecycle	We have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development	reflected in the policies & practices	INIST CSF, Security Development Lifecycle; Principles: Least privilege, Data minimisation; Knowledge management practices: System documentation, Unwritten rules followed by the teams							used for the partners?
10		VIII. Do you mention owners of the systems your smart system has integrations with as actors (3)?	We didn't mention the integrations with payment system providers	No	VIII. Do you mention owners of the systems your smart system has integrations with	Number of integrations: 1-2	as actors	Users: driver, car owners; Service providers: AVIS, Paypal, Payment system provider; Other stakeholders: Trusted Authority, City government, Local taxi firms							?
11		IX. Can the mentioned challenges be solved by using the respective standards (4)?		Yes	IX. Can the mentioned challenges	interoperability, availability	be solved by using the following standards?	Principles: Least privilege, Data minimisation; Knowledge management practices: System documentation, Unwritten rules followed by the teams; Coordination of policies with partners: enabling; Training for users: introducing the private policy; during the first-time onboarding to the system; Training for employees: we don't have							?
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- If needed, adjust the FISP-ProCOP matrix (columns H and I in the sheet “Answers in matrix”) in the created copy of FISP-ProCOP Analyser, if it helps you to specify the situation in your company better than what is depicted through the questionnaire.
- The validation results with “No” are the identified inconsistencies among the measures for information security and privacy management. Such inconsistencies can be used as the baseline for the requirements.

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